

PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SELF-DEVELOPMENT OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF PHYSICAL CULTURE

E.T. Djurabekov

Associate Professor at the Tashkent Institute of Economics and Pedagogy

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Abstract. *The article discusses the pedagogical foundations of professional self-development of future teachers of Physical Culture. The main aspects include taking into account the individual and age characteristics of students, encouraging their self-improvement in the process of professional activity, as well as providing the opportunity to choose a personal trajectory of self-improvement, taking into account the guidelines for professional development.*

Keywords: *pedagogical technology of self-improvement in the process of professional activity, teachers of Physical Culture, pedagogical process.*

It is important to suggest that one of the priorities of our country's policy is to educate a physically and spiritually healthy generation. Indeed, in the modern conditions of intensifying globalization processes in the countries of the world, educating a highly spiritual and physically developed generation is one of the most important factors determining the future of our Motherland and realizing the noble goals of our people. A legal basis for this noble cause has also been created, large-scale work is underway. The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev dated June 3, 2017 PR-3031 "On measures to develop physical culture and mass sports" and the Resolution "On physical culture and sports" dated March 5, 2017, the decree PD-5368 dated 2018 "On measures to radically improve the public administration system in the field of education" are of particular importance in the further development of this area. One of the main goals of these decrees and resolutions is to further deepen theoretical and practical knowledge in this area, correctly formulate concepts and terms related to skills and qualifications in the field of physical education.

Definitely, a radical reform of the education system creates a need for a new generation of teachers who are competitive both nationally and globally.

Certainly, the introduction of innovative technologies in the educational process and the transition to a global education system significantly change the content of teachers' activities. The growing demand for teachers in the higher education system who work in accordance with world standards creates a need for continuous education. However, the lack of funding for centralized teacher training courses necessitates the search for alternative methods of teacher training. Therefore, self-improvement, independent learning and self-education play an important role in the daily activities of a teacher.

Moreover, most teachers of educational institutions believe that the main tasks of a teacher in organizing and managing the pedagogical process are organizing and managing the educational process on a scientific basis, providing students with the necessary information on issues related to the educational process. In our opinion, in the process of organizing and managing the pedagogical process, teachers need to solve the following particularly important tasks:

- determining the educational and developmental goals of the educational process in accordance with the topic planned for study in the curriculum;

- setting tasks in accordance with the goal and preliminary planning of activities that need to be organized to achieve the desired results, choosing the directions for their implementation and the pedagogical technologies used.

However, any improvement should be carried out according to the planned program, so teachers should plan self-improvement in the process of professional activity and know the tools of self-development.

Therefore, one of the functional tasks of teachers in educational institutions is to coordinate the activities of students as subjects of the educational process and increase their activity to achieve the goal of pedagogical processes, and they, in turn, are engaged in self-education. They manage their own activities, in short, the educational process, which in turn is a joint management activity of teachers and students, based on friendly relations.

On the history, traditions, methods and directions of sports development in Uzbekistan there can be suggested A.K.Atoev, J.Nurshin, R.Salomov, F.Kerimov, Sh.Kh.Khonkeldiev, J.M.Toshpulatov, O.I.Ibrokhimov, A.N.Abdiev, who conducted research on the issues of modern organization of physical education classes and training of future personnel with scientific potential.

Besides that, K.M.Mahkamjonov, I.A.Koshbakhtiev, L.R.Ayrapetyan, T.S.Usmonkhodjaev, S.S.Khodjaev, K.Alimov conducted research on the development of national sports and design of sports clubs. Methods of organizing hikes are reflected in the works of T.Kh.Kholdarov, R.Abdumalikov, R.A.Kosimov, A.Abdullaev as well as prominent scientists (Yu. Babansky, A. Nisimchuk, H. Selevko, S. Sysoeva, others) paid particular attention to the issues of pedagogical technologies and their application in the educational process. At the same time, it should be noted that pedagogical technologies are mainly aimed at improving the training of future specialists.

On the other hand, the issue of improving the professional level of working teachers (especially physical education teachers) has not yet been fully studied. The work of a physical education teacher in modern conditions requires constant updating of knowledge, improvement of pedagogical communication, personal physical capabilities, and the ability to use information technology. All these factors encourage teachers to engage in systematic and continuous self-improvement in order to develop their personal qualities.

Definitely, the study of scientific literature and the study of the work experience of physical education teachers in higher educational institutions made it possible to identify a number of contradictions between the current level of professional skills of physical education teachers and modern requirements for their activities. High demands made by society and the state in the Bologna process on the continuous education of physical education teachers, and the lack of sufficient attention to this issue on the part of the teachers themselves; the need for teachers to master modern pedagogical technologies of self-improvement in the process of professional activity and the insufficient development of the theoretical foundations of self-improvement.

Objective is to identify pedagogical conditions for the effective implementation of the pedagogical foundations of self-development in the process of professional activity of physical education teachers. The implementation of the pedagogical technology of professional self-improvement of physical education teachers is based on solving the following problems:

Professional self-development and improvement of physical education teachers includes motivational, activity, information-operational and communicative components. The level of these components is determined by the level of need and motivation (the presence of cognitive interest;

significant needs and motives for self-improvement; a certain level of existing internal motivation, self-awareness; value attitude to pedagogical activity; understanding the essence of pedagogical activity) can be assessed with the help of continuous and systematic improvement of professional skills throughout life, acquisition of functional (ability to use methods and means of improving physical qualities; ability to assess physical fitness; ability to assess and self-assess), theoretical and methodological knowledge. Forms of conducting healthy lifestyle lessons, basic teaching methods, basic means of physical education and their implementation in the educational process; knowledge of innovative approaches, communication (ability to communicate in the form of a monologue, dialogue and conversation), use of gestures, facial expressions, pantomime in lessons; use of professional terms in pedagogical activities, etc., as well as information and operational criteria (Internet tools and office programs when working with a computer, various data sources, computer operating system, ability to work with Moodle in the educational process) for the professional development of physical education teachers. The level of self-improvement can be low, medium and high.

Conclusion. By summarizing it should be suggested that one of the most important factors in the further development of physical culture and sports in our country is the potential of specialized personnel in this area. Therefore, it is advisable to fully meet the requirements for the system of training personnel in the field of physical culture and sports, and also to a certain extent enrich this system with new requirements based on the proposals presented above.

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